

2D Topological Insulator states in transitional metal dichalcogenides

Version 1

Description

Purpose of the DMP is to manage experimental data acquired during the implementation of the project lzp-2024/1-0231, "2D Topological Insulator states in transitional metal dichalcogenides". Project leader Dr. Chem. Gunta Kunakova, 01.01.2025. - 31.12.2027., 300 000.00 EUR.

This plan will be structured based on the planned deliverables - open access scientific publications. The Data will be experimental data on charge transport measurements and magnetotransport characteristics of new WTe₂/hBN heterostructures and nanostructure devices. These experimental data will be used in preparation of 6 manuscripts, which will be available within the open access publications and their supporting information files once they are published.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

2D Topological Insulator states
in transitional metal
dichalcogenides (lzp-2024/1-
0231)

Researchers

Gunta Kunakova (0000-0003-0243-2678)

Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [2D Topological Insulator states in transitional metal dichalcogenides](#)

Description:

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Researchers:

[Gunta Kunakova \(0000-0003-0243-2678\)](#)

Organizations:

[University of Latvia](#)

Contact: [Kunakova Gunta \(gunta.kunakova@lu.lv\)](mailto:gunta.kunakova@lu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#)

Grants: [2D Topological Insulator states in transitional metal dichalcogenides \(Izp-2024/1-0231\)](#)

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2025-03-31](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

2D TI TMDs heterostructures: growth, characterisation, device fabrication and charge transport

Project activity plan:

<WP1> 2D TI TMDs – materials: [growth], [characterisation]

<WP2> Characterisation using spectroscopy methods: [characterisation]

<WP3> Structural investigations: [characterisation]

<WP4> Nanodevice fabrication: [device fabrication]

<WP5> Studies of the TI states: [charge transport]

Data:

[growth] - variety of microscopy images (*.tiff, *.jpg, *.ibw, files)

[characterisation] - spectroscopy data (mostly *.dat files)

[device fabrication] - variety of microscopy images and process flows (*.tiff, *.jpg, *.ibw, *.xls files)

[charge transport] - magnetotransport data: gate, angle and temperature dependencies (*.dat files)

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Purpose of the data acquisition and collection is to achieve state-of-the-art 2D topological insulator transitional metal dichalcogenide materials serving as the ultimate testbed for reproducibly harnessing the QSH effect.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- CSV
- TIFF
- Others

IBW, ASCII, DAT

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

2D materials being developed within the framework of this project is not demonstrated , no similar data available

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers working on fundamental studies of nanoelectronic materials and devices based on TMD/h-BN heterostructures and other 2D materials

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

measurement set-up, sample batch

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Data will be open only once the deliverables based on these data are published as open access publications. Till then, the data will be "restricted, request access".

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

excel, notepad, gwyddon

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-01-09

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

Costs will be covered by the project

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Gunta Kunakova (0000-0003-0243-2678)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

During the project implementation, all data will be duplicated and stored in the University of Latvia Share point and Google Drive accounts, available via two-factor authentication. All data recorded using a variety of microscopy methods and physical property measurement system will be stored, as originally recorded, on the hard drives of the scientific instrument computers.

After the project implementation, the data will be retained on the scientific instrument computer disks for at least 5 years, and online (Sharepoint).

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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